

Formation of *N,N'*-bis[1-(2-hydroxyphenyl)ethylidene]ethylenediamine in the reaction of 1-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-3-(*N,N*-dimethylamino)propenone with ethylenediamine

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Abstract : Ethylenediamine reacts with 1-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-3-(*N,N*-dimethylamino)propenone **3** to form *N,N'*-bis[1-(2-hydroxyphenyl)ethylidene]ethylenediamine **2** instead of the expected bisenaminoketone **1**.

Keywords : Ethylenediamine, chromone, bisenamine.

Introduction

Reaction of ethylenediamine with chromone¹ or chromone-2-carboxylic acid² leads to the formation of 2,3-dihydro-5/7-(2'-hydroxyphenyl)-1,4-diazepine as major product. The reaction takes place by the initial attack of amine at C-2 position of chromone moiety and subsequently cyclisation takes place by the attack of second amino function of ethylenediamine at the C-4 position of chromone ring. Similar reaction of ethylenediamine with 4-chlorocoumarin has recently been reported from our laboratory³. The first attack of amine at C-2 position and not at the C-4 position of 4-chlorocoumarin for the formation of 2,3,4,5-tetrahydro-7-(2'-hydroxyphenyl)-1,4-diazepin-5-one has also been established. It has been reported that depending on the reaction condition ethylenediamine reacts with chromone or chromone-2-carboxylic acid to form symmetrical bisenamine **1**, Schiff base **2** in minor amounts along with the 1,4-diazepine^{1,2}.

The symmetrical structure of the bisenamine **1** drew our attention because it can be considered as O, N-donor hexadentate ligand for the formation dinuclear complexes. β -*N,N*-Dimethylaminopropenone **3**⁴ has proved itself to be a very good substrate for the regioselective attack by nitrogenous nucleophile at the β -position of the enamine **3**⁵. With an endeavour to synthesize **1** in good yield, enaminoketone **3** was reacted with ethylenediamine. The result of the reaction is reported in this communication.

An ethanolic solution of enaminoketone **3** and ethylenediamine (in 2 : 1 molar ratios) was heated under re-

flux for 30 h. After usual work up, it afforded a yellow crystalline solid in low yield (20%) along with some unreacted material. The yellow compound was found to be the Schiff base **2** from spectral analysis (vide Experimental). Structure of compound **2** was further confirmed by its individual synthesis. An ethanolic solution of *o*-hydroxyacetophenone (2 equivalents) and ethylenediamine (1 equivalent) produces **2** in good yield on heating under reflux for 3 h (Scheme 1).

At first it was assumed that the enaminoketone **3** may undergo retroaldol type reaction to produce *o*-hydroxyacetophenone, which then further reacts with ethylenediamine to produce **2**. But ethanol alone failed to effect any change on enaminoketone **3** even after heating under reflux for 30 h. So, ethylenediamine has some role

Scheme 1

behind this retroaldol type reaction. To check whether the basic property of ethylenediamine is responsible for such retrogression, the enaminketone **3** was heated in ethanol in presence of 2 equivalents of pyridine, but no change was observed even after heating for 20 h.

Ethylenediamine or 1,3-diaminopropane reacts with 2-*N,N*-dialkylaminochromone to undergo substitution at the 2-position of chromone ring⁶. 2-*N,N*-Dimethylaminochromone-3-carbaldehyde is much more reactive for substitution by α,ω -diaminoalkanes⁷. Similar reactions on 2-(*N*-methyl-*N*-phenyl)aminochromone-3-carbaldehyde with ethylenediamine or 1,3-diaminopropane⁸ and *o*-phenylenediamine⁹ have been reported. The differences in reactivity of aliphatic and aromatic diamines have been predicted. Although *o*-phenylenediamine forms a diazepine derivative⁹, ethylenediamine forms methylideneimidazole by performing attack at C-2 position of chromone moiety by both the amino nitrogen atoms of ethylenediamine^{7,8}.

A plausible mechanism for the formation of **2** from **3** in the presence of ethylenediamine is depicted in Scheme 2. Substitution of NMe₂ group of **3** by amino function of ethylenediamine takes place by an addition-elimination sequence to form **4**, where the second amino function undergoes intramolecular Michael type addition and turns it into **5**, which forms *o*-hydroxyacetophenone via enol **6** with the expulsion of an imidazoline moiety. *o*-Hydroxyacetophenone then reacts with ethylenediamine to form **2**. It should be mentioned here that no spot corresponding to *o*-hydroxyacetophenone was observed in TLC during monitoring the progress of the reaction. It may be due to (a) very low concentration of *o*-hydroxyacetophenone in the medium, and/or (b) its faster rate of reaction with ethylenediamine than its formation from **3**. The proposed mechanism deserves 1.5 equivalents of ethylenediamine per mole of enaminketone **3**. The reaction of **3** with ethylenediamine in 1 : 2 molar

ratios was indeed found to be complete in 10 h when heated under reflux in ethanol.

To check the feasibility of the reaction with 1,3-diaminopropane, compound **3c** was heated with 1,3-diaminopropane in 1 : 2 molar ratio in ethanol under reflux for 8 h and after usual work up it produced **7** (Fig. 1), a higher homologue of **2c**.

Fig. 1

In conclusion, we have rationalized the formation of *o*-hydroxyacetophenone-ethylenediamine Schiff base **2** from the reaction of enaminketone **3** with ethylenediamine.

Experimental

The recorded melting points are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded in KBr on a Beckman IR 20A, ¹H NMR spectra on a Bruker 300 MHz spectrometer and mass spectra on Qtof Micro YA 263 instrument. Light petroleum ether refers to the fraction with distillation range 60–80 °C.

Reaction of 1-(2-hydroxy-5-substitutedphenyl)-3-(*N,N*-dimethylamino)propenones **3** with ethylenediamine :

An ethanolic solution of **3** (1 mmol) and ethylenediamine (120 mg, 2 mmol) was heated under reflux for 10 h. Solvent from the reaction mixture was removed under reduced pressure. Addition of ice cold water (10 ml) to the concentrate produced a solid, which was filtered, washed with water and dried in air. The solid residue was recrystallised from benzene-light petroleum ether to afford a yellow crystalline solid *N,N'*-bis[1-(2-hydroxy-5-substitutedphenyl)ethylidene]ethylenediamine **2**.

2a : Yield (90 mg, 61%); m.p. 188–190 °C; ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) : 3450, 2960, 1615, 1500; δ_{H} (CDCl₃) : 2.39 (6H, s, 2 × CH₃), 3.98 (4H, s, 2 × CH₂), 6.76–6.82 (2H, m, 2 × H-5), 6.92 (2H, dd, *J* 8.3, 0.9 Hz, 2 × H-3), 7.25–7.30 (2H, m, 2 × H-4), 7.52 (2H, dd, *J* 8.0, 1.2 Hz, 2 × H-6) and 15.84 (2H, brs, exchangeable, 2 × OH); MS : *m/z* 297 (M + H⁺).

2b : Yield (100 mg, 55%); m.p. 236–238 °C; ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) : 3447, 2910, 1615, 1492; δ_{H} (CDCl₃) : 2.38 (6H, s, 2 × CH₃), 4.00 (4H, s, 2 × CH₂), 6.88 (2H, d,

Scheme 2

Note

J 9.0 Hz, $2 \times$ H-3), 7.23 (2H, dd, J 9.0, 0.9 Hz, $2 \times$ H-4), 7.50 (2H, d, J 0.9 Hz, $2 \times$ H-6) and 15.76 (2H, brs, exchangeable, $2 \times$ OH).

2c : Yield (100 mg, 62%); m.p. 200–202 °C; ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}) : 3450, 2917, 1618, 1512.

Compounds **2a-c** are identical in all respect (m.p., m.m.p and superimposable IR) with the samples prepared from appropriate hydroxyacetophenones and ethylenediamine.

Reaction of 1-(2-hydroxy-5-methylphenyl)-3-(N,N-dimethylamino)propenones 3c with 1,3-diaminopropane :

An ethanolic solution of **3c** (205 mg, 1 mmol) and 1,3-diaminopropane (150 mg, 2 mmol) was heated under reflux for 8 h. Ethanol was removed under reduced pressure and ice-water (15 g) was added to the yellow oily concentrate. The separated yellow solid was filtered off, dried in air and recrystallised from benzene-light petroleum ether to afford a yellow crystalline solid *N,N'*-bis-[1-(2-hydroxy-5-methylphenyl)ethylidene]-1,3-diaminopropane **7**.

7 : Yield (110 mg, 65%); m.p. 120–122 °C; ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}) : 3448, 2920, 1618, 1505 ; δ_{H} (CDCl_3) : 2.21 (2H, quintet, J 6.4 Hz, CH_2), 2.27 (6H, s, $2 \times$ CH_3), 2.32 (6H, s, $2 \times$ CH_3), 3.71 (4H, t, J 6.4 Hz, $2 \times$ CH_2), 6.84 (2H, d, J 8.3 Hz, $2 \times$ H-3), 7.09 (2H, dd, J 8.3, 1.6 Hz, $2 \times$ H-4), 7.35 (2H, d, J 1.6 Hz, $2 \times$ H-

6) and 16.07 (2H, brs, exchangeable, $2 \times$ OH).

Compound **7** is also found to be identical in all respect with the sample prepared from 2-hydroxy-5-methylacetophenone and 1,3-diaminopropane.

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